

Sustainability plan (D5.4)

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Introduction

The sustainability plan concerns primarily the EU Open Research Repository. The EU Open Research Repository was launched as a pilot in March 2024 and is expected to be fully operational by autumn 2024. This repository allows researchers to share and preserve outputs from Horizon Europe (including ERC and MCSA), as well as earlier Framework Programmes and Euratom, across all subject areas. Additionally, EU-funded research projects can request an EU project community, which allows them to manage research outputs from their projects. The repository will later expand with FAIR-enabling features and other functionalities to facilitate compliance with the open science requirements of the Horizon Europe grant agreement.

The EU Open Research Repository is operated and managed by CERN on behalf of the European Commission through the HORIZON-ZEN project (2023-2025). The repository is technically a Zenodo community, which is operated as part of Zenodo, offered by CERN as part of its mission to make the results of its work available.

Zenodo is legally owned by CERN and operated on CERN's data centers. CERN has built and operated Zenodo over the past 12 years with co-funding primarily from the European Commission, together with project partners such as OpenAIRE. Zenodo operates as a thin layer on top of CERN's existing technical and organizational infrastructure for high-energy physics and the Large Hadron Collider.

The operation of the EU Open Research Repository as a service requires, at a minimum, coverage of the following high-level areas:

- **Support to users** - handling of general enquiries, quota increases, take-down requests, file modifications etc.
- **Curation of research outputs** - review of requests to create EU project communities, curation of records submitted outside an EU project community, overall monitoring, and quality assurance of content in the repository.
- **Outreach/training** - writing and updating of end-user documentation, FAQs and text pages; organization of outreach activities such as webinars, newsletters and blog posts.
- **Infrastructure operations** - 24/7 operation and maintenance of the technical infrastructure running Zenodo (including security updates, handling increased growth, backup etc)
- **Governance/management** - management and coordination of the EU Open Research Repository, decision making on policies and legal matters, collaborations with other initiatives.
- **Development** - continued maintenance of the source code base as well as smaller improvements to the overall platform.

Note, some of these areas are handled centrally for all of Zenodo, while others (e.g. curation) is specifically only for the EU Open Research Repository.

Governance

The EU Open Research Repository operates under a multi-layered governance structure due to its operation as a Zenodo community and Zenodo being an instance of the technical InvenioRDM platform.

EU Open Research Repository

The governance of the Zenodo community, which constitutes the EU Open Research Repository, is fully under the European Commission (EC). The EC holds full responsibility for the governance of this community, including establishing a curation policy that determines the scope of submissions allowed in the repository. This policy can be modified by the EC at their discretion to adapt to evolving needs or priorities.

The Zenodo community operates within the broader context of the Zenodo service and is thus constrained by Zenodo's policies, most notably the [Terms of Use](#) and [General Policies](#). These policies are currently less restrictive than those imposed by the European Commission, providing a flexible environment for the repository's operation. The main restriction is that Zenodo is only for non-military purposes due to CERN's purpose, as established in the CERN Convention, which states:

“The Organization shall have no concern with work for military requirements and the results of its experimental and theoretical work shall be published or otherwise made generally available.”

Zenodo

Zenodo itself is owned by CERN, which is governed by its member states, 18 of which are EU member states out of a total of 23. The daily management and operational responsibilities of Zenodo fall under the CERN IT Department, which defines the policies and oversees the service's operation and functionality.

Additionally, oversight for Zenodo is provided by CERN's Scientific Information Policy Board and the CERN Open Science Steering Board, ensuring alignment with CERN's broader scientific and open science objectives. As an entity, Zenodo is subject to CERN's legal status as an intergovernmental organization, which provides a unique governance framework distinct from typical national or private institutions.

CERN is a large intergovernmental research organization with a strong international reputation and is already the custodian of the Large Hadron Collider data and a memory institute for High-Energy Physics. Operating Zenodo as part of CERN ensures that Zenodo benefits from economies of scale and the capital and operational investments CERN makes to support its scientific program, allowing Zenodo to be operated cost-efficiently as a thin layer on top of the core technical and organizational infrastructure.

InvenioRDM

Zenodo is operated on top of the InvenioRDM repository platform, which is subject to [Invenio Governance](#). The InvenioRDM community currently consists of 27 partner organizations from across the world who lead the development of the technical platform. These 27 organizations provide services to a wide variety of researchers from across the globe and scientific fields, ensuring that the development of the technical platform takes into account best practices and user needs from these services.

Governance needs

Zenodo currently does not have any formally defined governance structures for community input and direct oversight. For instance, Zenodo has only had ad-hoc scientific editorial oversight boards to handle specific cases. While we've been good at listening to users and supporting their needs, the scientific community does not have a direct say in Zenodo through established governance structures, aside from CERN's governance.

Zenodo has grown over the years, and regular editorial oversight is becoming increasingly important both due to the rise of misinformation and to demonstrate transparency and trust to the community. For the EU Open Research Repository, this would mean that the European Commission would benefit from a well-established governance structure to influence Zenodo, rather than through the current method of grant funding.

Any new governance structures for Zenodo should take into consideration aspects such as:

- Best practices – ensuring that the governance structure aligns with community defined principles for open scholarly infrastructures.
- Community – ensuring the community is represented in the governance structures to provide input on the strategic direction of Zenodo and that Zenodo serves the community's needs.
- Transparency – ensuring transparency in operations, selection of members as well appropriate oversight.
- Ethics – ensuring operation according to high scientific and ethical standards.
- Financing – ensuring Zenodo is attractive to co-finance by e.g. linking decision making power with investments and ensuring a sustainable financial model for the long-term.
- Visibility – ensuring Zenodo gains visibility in the larger Open Science movement.
- Diversity – reflecting both CERN's Code of Conduct as well as Zenodo's image as a progressive service for Open Science.
- Innovation – ensuring the ability to continue leading at the cutting-edge of Open Science.
- Technical Platform – ensuring that the governance structures aligns with the governance of the technical platform and that the governance structures maximize impact of both the service and the technical platform.

Legally, CERN has examples such as the SCOAP3 partnership (Sponsoring Consortium for Open Access Publishing in Particle Physics), which could serve as a model for establishing multi-stakeholder governance for Zenodo, where CERN acts as a Host Organization.

Legal considerations

Legal status

Zenodo operates within the CERN legal framework. CERN is an intergovernmental organization with legal personality in the metropolitan territories of all CERN Member States (CERN Convention, Articles IX & XI) and enjoys the corresponding legal capacity under public international law.

As an intergovernmental organization, CERN enjoys certain privileges and immunities, including immunity from the jurisdiction of national courts to ensure its independence from individual Member States. This does not mean that CERN operates in a legal vacuum, as protocols require that CERN settle its disputes by other means, namely through arbitration.

Legal basis for collaborations

Memorandum of Understanding

CERN and the European Commission have concluded [a Memorandum of Understanding](#) (MoU) in 2009, which outlines their intent to cooperate, particularly concerning research programming, training and mobility of researchers, research infrastructures, management of intellectual property, and international collaboration. The MoU is implemented through bi-annual work plans, approved by the Director-General of CERN and the Director-General of the EC Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD).

Collaboration agreements

CERN concludes numerous agreements each year to cover scientific and technical collaborations with scientific institutions, universities, funding agencies, public bodies, and other entities.

Collaboration agreements are used to define scientific and technical collaborations between CERN, on the one hand, and institutes located in a CERN Member or Associate Member State, on the other hand. These collaborations are typically implemented through projects. A defining element of a collaboration agreement is that there is a reasonable balance (though not necessarily in equal proportions) between CERN's contribution and that of the other parties. Collaboration agreements can take the form of either framework agreements (open-ended duration) or specific agreements (one-off projects).

Framework agreements first set out the potential areas of mutual scientific and technological interest between CERN and the institute, followed by provisions relating to the appointment of the parties' experts, intellectual property, publications, confidentiality, liability, governing law, and dispute resolution. Each individual project under the framework agreement must be defined in a detailed addendum to the framework agreement.

Specific agreements, on the other hand, define a project in a single document, including its duration, each party's contribution of resources, and any deliverables, milestones, and acceptance procedures. They also cover standard provisions relating to the selection and appointment of experts, conduct and safety, intellectual property, publications, confidentiality, and liability.

CERN has had and continues to have several such specific collaboration agreements with the European Commission.

Call for tenders

As a publicly funded research institution, CERN cannot compete with commercial entities and therefore cannot participate in calls for tenders.

Personal data

Processing of personal data at CERN is governed by [CERN's Operational Circular 11](#) (OC11), which offers data protection standards comparable to the EU's GDPR and the Swiss FADP. Therefore, CERN processes personal data solely in accordance with its internal legislation. CERN's data privacy framework builds on principles established in its Member States and the European Union, implemented through technical and organizational measures.

CERN has established an independent supervisory authority, the Data Protection Commission, which is mandated to monitor CERN's compliance with OC11, ensure the application of OC11 (particularly regarding data subject rights), and evaluate and investigate complaints lodged by data subjects, regardless of their connection to CERN.

Transfer of personal data

Zenodo has a detailed [privacy policy](#) that outlines which personal data we process and retain, the purposes and legal bases for processing, who has access, and which personal data we may transfer to others, including the recipients and purposes of such transfers.

The current privacy policy permits the transfer of all research outputs, including metadata and publicly available data, to the general public. Thus, the policy allows for the transfer of research outputs themselves, except for restricted files, to another entity such as the European Commission. This is relevant if the European Commission wishes to move the EU Open Research Repository out of Zenodo.

However, the privacy policy does not allow for the transfer of personal data, such as end-user accounts. Therefore, if the European Commission wishes to transfer end-user accounts and restricted files, each user would need to provide consent for their data to be transferred.

Ownership of the source code

Zenodo, InvenioRDM, and the entire underlying infrastructure (including the database, storage system software, search engine index, load balancers, message queue, etc.) are open source, enabling anyone to run, use, and modify the full software stack. All software is licensed under an Open Source Initiative (OSI) approved license. InvenioRDM is primarily MIT licensed, while certain parts of Zenodo are GPL licensed.

Ownership of the data

All research outputs uploaded to Zenodo by end-users remain the intellectual property of their respective owners. The use of Zenodo is governed by Zenodo's Terms of Use, which stipulate that there is no transfer of intellectual property rights to CERN when content is uploaded.

Legal needs

CERN and the European Commission already have both high-level agreements and numerous collaboration agreements. The continued operation of the EU Open Research Repository on top of Zenodo could thus be based on the CERN-EC MoU combined with the signing of a collaboration agreement specifically for the EU Open Research Repository. This could be complemented by establishing a more direct formal governance structure for Zenodo than the current one.

Furthermore, exit strategies for moving the EU Open Research Repository should consider the need for end-users to consent to the transfer of their user accounts to another platform, most notably to allow end-users to continue editing the metadata of their research outputs. Besides the need for consent to transfer user accounts, there are no legal obstacles or lock-ins for moving the EU Open Research Repository out of Zenodo, as the entire platform is open source (i.e., data can be transferred fairly easily to a replicated platform), and the research outputs themselves are openly available.

Estimation of costs

The high-level areas needed to operate the EU Open Research Repository are covered in the section "Introduction," including support to users, curation of research outputs, outreach/training, infrastructure operation, development, and governance/management.

Expenses

Outlined below are the major categories of expenses that are necessary to operate and maintain the EU Open Research Repository.

Personnel

Covering the above mentioned areas for operating the EU Open Research Repository require the following functions:

- Librarian/Information specialist (curation, quality control, outreach, training)
- Supporter (end-user support and request handling)
- Computing engineer (operations, development)
- Manager

Administrative personnel such as legal, financial, project support and other organizational functions at CERN which are also required to operate Zenodo are excluded from this list.

The team operating Zenodo currently consists of:

- 1 FTE manager
- 2 FTE experienced staff
- 4 FTE junior staff

We estimate the EU Open Research Repository's share of the personnel cost to be in the order of **0.3 FTE experienced staff and 0.4 FTE junior staff** with the following disclaimers:

- Numbers are approximative and likely higher in practice due certain usage being difficult to estimate and account for.
- The librarian/information specialist function is not part of the current activities of the personnel and hence in addition to above numbers (see estimation in "Growth estimation" section below).
- Zenodo has always had very minimal outreach and training and instead relied on partners for a large part of the outreach effort which is thus also not included in above estimates.
- These numbers do not take repository growth into account.

Infrastructure

Zenodo is operated as a thin layer on top of CERN's existing technical infrastructure. It uses a suite of underlying IT services such as provisioned databases, storage clusters, application hosting, monitoring, security, and more. These services are also provided internally to CERN's user communities, typically at a much larger scale than Zenodo. Internal costing of CERN services has shown that approximately 90% of Zenodo's costs are related to personnel expenses, while only 10% of the costs are related to technical infrastructure.

Growth estimation

The detailed growth estimation of the EU Open Research Repository is covered in the appendix. The growth is estimated over a five-year period from 2024 to 2029 based on historic growth. These estimations naturally have large uncertainties and can be significantly influenced in both directions by factors such as policy changes. The key numbers from the estimation are:

Metric	2024	2029
Data volume	64 TB	240 TB
Records	112,000	230,000
EU Project Communities	2,725	7,000-10,000
Curation records/month	100	300-650
Curation communities/month	70	70-250
Support requests/month	25	50

Share of EC projects

Currently, 23% of all EU-funded research projects have minimum one research output preserved on Zenodo. 5% of all projects also have a Zenodo-community on Zenodo.

Personnel needs

Overall, the operation of the EU Open Research Repository will require to fund in the order of

Personnel needs	FTE
Curation (excluding support, training, outreach etc)	0.5-1.5
Support, training, outreach, quality control	0.5
Experienced staff (management, infrastructure, development)	0.3
Junior staff (infrastructure, development)	0.4

The tasks most affected by usage growth are the curation efforts as well as the interactions with end-users such as support and request handling. The functions required to run and operate the infrastructure are less affected by growth.

Note the estimates are minimal and cover only the basic operation.

Cost reduction options

The following section includes suggestions for how the operational costs of the EU Open Research Repository could be contained as the scale of usage increases. Note there may be additional development costs associated with the introduction of each cost reduction option.

Do not allow direct submission

A significant contributing factor to the costs is the effort required to curate directly submitted records to the EU Open Research Repository, instead of having EU project communities curate the records themselves. A way to lower the overall curation costs is to require all submissions to be made via an EU project community or harvested automatically.

Implementing this option is straightforward, but it may reduce the overall user experience and lead to the loss of a small fraction of research outputs. The latter issue can be addressed with a one-off investment in automating the harvesting process, including the enrichment of records.

Automate curation with generative AI

Another method to lower the required human curation effort is to automate the curation process. This approach would also benefit the EU project communities and lead to the largest overall reduction in curation efforts for everyone involved in curating the content of the EU Open Research Repository.

Advances in artificial intelligence, particularly generative AI and the release of open source models, mean that curation tasks can now be more easily automated. The main effort has shifted from AI model development to standard software development. The overall goal of automating curation is to reduce the required human curation effort to a bare minimum.

Automate request handling

Similarly, automating interactions with users, such as handling requests (e.g., takedown requests, quota increases, file modifications, and similar tasks), can lead to an overall reduction in the required effort. For example, automating the handling of quota increase requests can streamline processes and free up human resources for more complex tasks.

By implementing these automation solutions, the efficiency of managing the EU Open Research Repository can be significantly improved, ensuring a more sustainable operation.

Other considerations

European Open Science Cloud (EOSC)

The EU Open Research Repository will need to closely follow and integrate with [EOSC](#) as it evolves, particularly with the [EOSC EU Node](#). The EOSC EU Node is contracted out by the European Commission and is considered a service owned by the European Commission, similar to the Open Research Europe publishing platform. On the other hand, the EU Open Research Repository is a service owned by CERN and is thus considered a third-party provider for the EOSC EU Node.

Compliance

The introduction of new legislation and requirements may impact the costs of Zenodo and the EU Open Research Repository. For example, the introduction of the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) was mirrored by CERN in Operational Circular 11, introducing both implementation and operational costs.

In the coming years, Zenodo and the EU Open Research Repository may become subject to several compliance requirements in areas such as environmental impact, use of artificial intelligence, and cybersecurity. For instance, the NIS 2 Directive could require the enhancement of cybersecurity measures and compliance protocols, including adopting comprehensive risk management strategies, ensuring robust incident detection and response capabilities, and complying with precise incident reporting requirements.

CERN's legal status as an intergovernmental organization means it is not subject to national jurisdiction. However, CERN consistently implements corresponding internal legislation to those in its member states, where a majority of countries are EU member states. This approach is exemplified by the alignment of GDPR with CERN's OC11.

Exit strategies

The primary risk of operating the EU Open Research Repository on Zenodo is its dependency on the continued operation of Zenodo. Additionally, the EU Open Research Repository is subject to the ongoing development of Zenodo, including the introduction of new features and policies. The exit strategies (detailed below) provide a route to migrate out of Zenodo as risk mitigation.

Possible exit strategies for the above two scenarios include:

- **Reduce service offering:** You could reduce the curation, end-user support, training, outreach and similar to reduce the cost of the EU Open Research Repository. Reduction

of service offering will however impact end-users negatively, and thus may create significant reputational risks where a termination of service might be preferred.

- **Termination of service:** The branding of the EU Open Research Repository could be removed, reducing it to a normal Zenodo-community and change to an archived state, that is to say it would no longer accept new deposits of material. Zenodo/CERN would still incur costs on the preservation of the content that was uploaded.
- **Migration to another platform (without consent):** The research outputs hosted in the EU Open Research Repository could be exported in multiple standard formats and provided in the Oxford Common Filesystem Layout (OCFL) which allows the record to be imported into another repository system. A direct import into another InvenioRDM instance would be easier as there's a direct mapping between the metadata models as well as the available feature set which will significantly reduce the cost of a migration. A particular complication is that the DOIs for the content should also be moved, which needs to be coordinated with DataCite. Development costs both for the export and import of the content should be foreseen in such a move. Zenodo/CERN could then deaccession the research outputs from Zenodo.
- **Migration to another platform (with consent):** As highlighted under the section Legal considerations, moving restricted files, user accounts and e.g. EU project communities would be subject to consent by the users which could be incomplete (i.e. not all users may grant permission to migrate their material) and time-consuming and as researchers do change host institutions so the migration would likely not cover all users/communities and restricted files.

Another scenario is that Zenodo is decided to be shut down. In this case, the EU Open Research Repository will no longer be able to operate on Zenodo. Possible exit strategies in such a scenario are similar to the three strategies mentioned above.

Most importantly, for all exit strategies, CERN and the European Commission must agree upfront on a preferred exit strategy if the EU Open Research Repository must be shut down or moved, and/or if Zenodo is shut down.

Operational models

The operational models presented below assume the continued operation of the EU Open Research Repository on Zenodo. As detailed in the exit strategies, it is also possible to migrate the EU Open Research Repository to another platform. The operational models look only at minimal approaches for the continued operation.

Legal basis

For all operational models, a collaboration agreement needs to be established between CERN and the European Commission for the continued operation of the EU Open Research Repository. As detailed in the section "Legal considerations" there are already existing examples

which a new agreement could be based on. The scope of the agreement should focus on the operation of the EU Open Research Repository.

Funding

The collaboration agreement would require funding from the European Commission as part of the collaboration agreement to cover related personnel and infrastructure costs for the operation.

CERN can continue to compete in Horizon Europe and future Framework Programmes for larger development tasks for the improvement of Zenodo (not specifically related to the EU Open Research Repository). Similarly, in-kind contribution to the development of the underlying platform InvenioRDM is also funded by the InvenioRDM partner organizations which help both sustain and maintain the platform. However, the sustainability plan would thus depend on the outcomes of competitive funding calls and hence would be subject to significant risks for which the mitigation plan may need to invoke the exit strategies described in this document.

The required costs for the operation are detailed in the section “Estimation of costs”.

Model 1: CERN

The first operation model is that CERN continues to operate all parts of the EU Open Research Repository on behalf of the European Commission. The advantage of this model is that the full operation is under the responsibility of a single entity. The disadvantage is that it can be more difficult to up/down scale e.g. curation capacity according to user needs.

Model 2: CERN + Outsourcing

The second funding model splits part of the operation of the EU Open Research Repository. CERN continues to operate the Zenodo, but the curation and end-user support for the EU Open Research Repository is outsourced. The outsourcing can either be performed by CERN or by the European Commission. Similarly, part of the feature developments could be outsourced.

The advantage of this model is that the outsourcing can more easily be up/down scaled according to the needs of the EU Open Research Repository. The disadvantage is the overhead of managing the outsourcing contract, possible issues with finding skilled contractors to outsource to, as well as potentially not having a single entity responsible for the operation.

Model 3: Multi-stakeholder

The third model is an extension of both model 1 and 2, in which the European Commission and CERN sets up a direct governance structure for Zenodo which is open for other funding bodies and research organizations to help govern and co-fund Zenodo. The [SCOAP3](#) partnership in

which CERN acts as a Host Organisation already provides an example of how such a collaboration could be set up.

Recommendations

The EU Open Research Repository is a crucial platform for managing and sharing research outputs funded by the European Commission. Its operation on Zenodo leverages CERN's robust technical infrastructure, providing a cost-effective and scalable solution.

However, there are inherent risks and challenges, particularly concerning the reliance on Zenodo's continued operation and the evolving legislative landscape.

- **Establish a specific collaboration agreement** between CERN and the European Commission for the continued operation of the EU Open Research Repository after the grant funding stops. Build the agreement using existing agreements already established between CERN and the EC.
- **Invest in automation early** to reduce the need for human curation with the overall goal to reduce operational costs. This includes developing AI-driven solutions for record curation and automating routine user requests.
- **Exit strategies:** Agree upfront on a preferred exit strategy with the European Commission to mitigate risks as well as strategies for both user consent and technical feasibility to ensure a smooth transition if needed.
- **Consider multi-stakeholder governance:** Explore the feasibility of setting up a direct governance structure for Zenodo, open to other funding bodies and research organizations. This model can provide shared governance and co-funding, bringing more resources and expertise to the operation as well as mitigate risk of operating EU Open Research Repository on Zenodo.

Appendix

Repository growth

This appendix estimates growth over the next five years (2024-2029). We focus on the growth of content and communities using the EU Open Research Repository rather than metrics like usage (views/downloads), as these parameters have the largest impact on required infrastructure and manpower.

The estimations are highly dependent on various factors and could be significantly lower or higher depending on other actions (e.g., increased outreach, changes in content policy, etc.). All estimations relate exclusively to the EU Open Research Repository.

We estimate in the following growth on the following parameters:

- **Data volume** - what is the estimated growth in data volume that we need to preserve for the long term.
- **Record volume** - what is the estimated growth in the number of records that needs to be curated.
- **Communities** - what is the estimated growth in the number of communities linked to an EU project that should be reviewed per year.
- **Grants** - what is the estimated growth in number of EU projects depositing one or more research outputs in the EU Open Research Repository.

The above parameters are used to estimate the required infrastructure and personnel needs for the next five years. All baselines are as of May 2024.

Data volume

We estimate data volume based on records already part of the EU Open Research Repository. The estimated data volume is logical (i.e., without replication copies and backups) and has been extracted from Zenodo's database.

Estimation:

- Baseline: 64 TB
- Yearly growth rate: 30% (lowest observed yearly growth rate during 2018-2025)
- Estimated in 2029: ~240 TB

Communities

The following estimation is based on the dataset provided in <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11257907>. Communities included in the dataset are those that could be linked to an EU project by having the project ID or acronym present in the community

identifier or title, or where the user provided the grant information. The list was manually curated after the matching process.

Estimation 1:

- Baseline: 2725 communities representing EU projects (70 new communities created per month)
- Yearly growth rate: 30% (observed growth rate Jan-May 2024).
- Estimated in 2029: 10.000 communities for EU projects (250 new communities created per month)

Estimation 2:

- Baseline: 2725 communities representing EU projects (70 new communities created per month)
- Yearly growth rate: constant at current rate of 70 new communities per month.
- Estimated in 2029: 6900 communities for EU projects

An EU project community hosts an average 30 records.

Grants

The average number of EU grants from FP7, Horizon 2020, Horizon Europe over the past 10 years is 4700 grants/year (based on CORDIS data¹). The EU Open Research Repository currently hosts research outputs linked to 11.000 different EU projects.

This means that:

- 23% of all EU projects have at least one research output hosted in the EU Open Research Repository.
- 5% of all EU projects have a Zenodo-community.

Records

Note below numbers exclude 300.000k records (herbarium sheet scans) which were deposited by the ICEDIG project.

Total number of records

Estimation 1:

- Baseline: 112k records
- Yearly growth: 18% (average from the last 5 years)
- Estimated in 2029: 256k records

Estimation 2:

- Baseline: 112k records

¹ <https://doi.org/10.2906/112117098108/11> and <https://doi.org/10.2906/112117098108/12> and <https://doi.org/10.2906/112117098108/20>

- Yearly growth: constant at current rate of 22.000 records/year (2023).
- Estimated in 2029: 222k records

Number of records curated by EU project communities

An EU project community hosts an average of 30 records. Given the estimated 6,900 to 10,000 EU project communities in 2029, they will have curated between 207,000 to 300,000 records, corresponding to at least 80% of the total number of records.

Number of records NOT curated by EU project communities

Based on the above estimations that at least 80% of records are curated by EU project communities, we can estimate that over the next five years, the core team will need to manually curate up to around 22,000 to 28,000 records over the 5 year period (constant vs. 18% yearly growth). This corresponds to between 300 to 650 records per month.

Currently, after two months of pilot operation, we have curated an average of 100 records per month.

Curation/support time handling

Based on the past two months of operation, we have made rough estimations on the current handling time for requests (numbers are for a skilled and trained curator):

- **Review and manual setup of an EU project community:** 20 minutes (note, we expect this to be reduced significantly when we automated the setup).
- **Curation of a record:** 5 minutes (1 minute for easy records, 10 minutes for difficult records).

With the above times for curation, combined with the estimated number of records to curate and EU project communities to review, we obtain a rough estimation of the required effort for the curation:

- Record curation: 86-170 working days
- EU project review: 35-125 working days (8-30 days if time is reduced to 5 minutes per project).

Support

We do not yet have sufficient data to estimate the number of support requests related to the EU Open Research Repository. Currently, Zenodo handles an average of 5,800 support requests per year. The standard handling time per support request is around 5-15 minutes (for a skilled, trained supporter). Certain support request types like take-down requests can be very time-consuming and take 8-16 hours. We estimate that approximately 600 requests a year will be related to the EU Open Research Repository thus requiring about **10-20 working days for support handling per year**.